

Indian National Congress and All India States Peoples Conference Impact on the Freedom struggle in Kashmir.

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Abstract:

The British had established a barrier between British India and Princely India, indirectly governing latter through hereditary princes. Kashmir, a princely state under Dogra monarchy rule, experienced widespread discontent due to a lack of socio-economic and political benefits. The objective of the Indian National Congress was to unify the Princely State and recognized India as fundamentally a single entity. The formation of All India States' Peoples' Conference was crucial for states people's movement, fostering political consciousness and a demand for responsible government. After Congress deleted the clause relating to non-interference, the All India State People Conference came closer to the Indian National Congress, had a far reaching impact on the politics of Indian states especially in Kashmir. Nehru, the Congress leader developed strong relations with Kashmir freedom leader Sheikh Abdullah, and through his political philosophy, the freedom struggle in Kashmir became ideologically more connected to the Indian National Congress. This ultimately promoted Muslim Conference leadership to change its agenda and nomenclature of the party into the National Conference in 1939. This had a far-reaching impact on the Kashmir freedom struggle particularly from its birth to 1947. The paper examines the impact of Indian National Congress and All India States People Conference policies and programs on Jammu and Kashmir politics, analyzes Nehru's efforts in secularizing politics, and investigates factors influencing Abdullah's shift towards nationalism.

Keywords: Jammu and Kashmir, Indian National Congress, Sheikh Abdullah, National Conference, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru

Introduction:

Before 1947, India had numerous princely states, at least 562 (some authorities list 564, 584, even 601) in all, spread throughout the Subcontinent, encompassing 45.3 percent of its land and having a population of 99 million, which constituted about a third of the British Indian Empire's extent. The majority of the states were predominantly Hindu, with only a half dozen being Muslim. These states, referred to as the Native States by Britishers, were ruled by Indian princes. The Princes, who were the Rulers of the States, were considered part of the Indian Empire as they recognized the Paramountcy of the British Crown. The states were not technically territories annexed by the British Government in the name of the Crown, although there may have been coercion by the British in the acceptance or imposed of Paramountcy. These states are unique in the world, and they vary not only in size but also in terms of their political and social landscapes. In addition to this, most of these states remained entirely feudal, while others remained largely backward. The largest states in India were Hyderabad, Kashmir, Mysore, Travancore, and Baroda etc., while the smaller states were in Kathiawar, Western India, and Punjab. British rulers in Princely States maintained and protected their autocratic polities, ensuring the protection and perpetual existence of the princes. Moreover, British authorities used princes to deter national unity and counter the rising national movement. These states had a monarchical system

of government and were perceived as tradition-bound and apathetic in progress. People in these states faced higher land taxes, non-protection of civil liberties, lack of modernization and discrimination in all public spheres. The princes ruled these states in an authoritarian manner, resulting in extreme economic and political disabilities for the people.

Jammu and Kashmir, a large princely state in British India, is over 80,000 square miles in area with large populations, some 4,021,616 of which 77 percent were Muslims, approximately 20 percent were Hindus, 1.5 percent were Sikhs, and 1 percent were Buddhists, and around 93.4% had illiteracy, according to the 1941 census. The State of Jammu and Kashmir was established in the 19th century by Dogra chieftain Gulab Singh. On March 16, 1846, the British Colonial Empire sold Jammu and Kashmir to Gulab Singh for 75 lakh rupees, or Nanakshahi rupees. As per the treaty, Kashmir, was to belong "forever, an independent possession, to Maharaja Gulab Sing and the heirs male of his body." Dogras have traditionally considered Jammu to be their home and Kashmir to be their obtained property. This propensity illustrates that they never had empathy with the Kashmiri people. The Dogra administration was thoroughly rotten; people were systematically oppressed and depressed; there was no liberty of person and no security of property in the state. People in Kashmir were suffering from severe challenges, and the administration of justice was arbitrary and biased. The majority of the

population, were cultivators, faced double tyranny and repression from the state government and feudal lords. The Kashmir state experienced the worst form of taxation, inhumane torture, and misappropriation of public funds, an utter lack of civil liberties and civic rights, and no freedom of the press. Socio-economic reforms were not undertaken, corruption persisted, the administration remained inefficient, and justice was non-existent in the overwhelming majority of the state under this regime. Kashmir probably faced the worst type of exploitation and the most extremist type of autocracy. The predominantly Muslim state faced extreme political, social, and economic challenges, with the majority Muslim population living in poor economic conditions and being governed like dumb-driven cattle. But from 1930 -1947, Jammu and Kashmir experienced tremendous political development, leading to a shift in public opinion in favor of national sentiments. It was owing to the rise of political consciousness in British India that gradually began to impact public opinion in the princely territories. The Britishers, however, took multiple actions explicitly aimed at preventing any encouragement from 'British India' to the formation of national sentiment among the people of the states. The Indian National Congress emerged against colonial exploitative policies, aiming to consolidate national unity and declare its primary goal as *swaraj*, or independence. The princely states, on the other hand, were not included in the domain for which *swaraj* was desired. The Congress adopted a paradoxical plan of recognizing the states as integral part of India while at the same time claiming that interference can harm the cause of the people in the states. Mahatma Gandhi's policy of 'non-interference', which began in the 1920s, persisted until the late 1930s. In contrast to Mahatma Gandhi's belief, Jawaharlal Nehru, a Congress leader who was passionate about national unity, took more radical approach to address states people's problems. With the formation of the All India States Peoples Conference accelerated the growth of state people's movements in the states as an outcome of various policies and activities of the British as well as the attitude and approach of Congress. In reality, the sheer existence of the conference, which symbolized India's essential unity, was a major event. Unsurprisingly, the people of the states unanimously demanded greater sympathy and cooperation, as well as the end of the non-interference policy. It was in the 1930s the movements started in British India by Indian nationalists in several states inspired and articulated genuine public grievances against their respective rulers had a major influence on the Indian states. Thus, the overwhelming success of the Congress and resolutions supporting the freedom struggle in the States had also significantly impacted the

political climate in Jammu and Kashmir. Indian nationalists were very concerned about the Dogras' authoritarian and arbitrary rule in the State of Jammu and Kashmir.

Indian National Congress and All India States' Peoples' Conference:

The national movement in British India raised political consciousness about democracy, responsible administration, and civil liberties. The Indian National Congress's success, despite limited in gaining concessions, led the Princely States to realize the need to organize first at the local and then at the national levels in order to have their grievances addressed. India's leaders recognized that the interests of the States people were interconnected with those under direct British rule. Mahatma Gandhi, Sarojini Naidu, Maulana Mohammad Ali, and Pandit Jawharlal Nehru were some of the leaders who belonged to the States or had close contact with them. Despite pressure from the state people and provocation by the rulers, the Indian National Congress, led by Mahatma Gandhi, remained committed to its policy of non interference in the internal affairs of the Native States. However, Congress allowed state people to enroll as members but refused to interfere in their state affairs. Gandhi considered this policy "wise and sound" and believed that "as darkness vanishes at sunrise so when the sun of *Swaraj* rises, the dark anarchy of rulers as well as of subjects will disappear in an instant". This approach continued until the mid-thirties.

Despite having sympathy for the State people, the Congress was hesitant to directly address their concerns. In December 1920, at its Nagpur session, the Congress passed a resolution urging princes to grant responsible government in their states, although its policy of non-interference continued. The growing interest and involvement of state people in national activities and the Congress's discouraging attitude prompted them to organise their own organisation, the All India States People Conference, in 1927. They thought that the fight for responsible government and civil freedoms in the state would have to be carried out by themselves thus, forming their own organization was necessary. They demanded the integration of the States People's movement and the general anti-imperialist struggle waged by Congress. On December 17, 1927, the first session of the AISPC took place in Bombay, attended by over 1,500 people and visitors from over 70 states. Ram Chandra Roa's presidential address aimed for a "free, strong, united, self-governing and self-supporting India". The inaugural session received wide publicity, highlighting the demand for "responsible government in the Indian States through representative institutions under the aegis of rulers and civil liberties." The conference, marking India's unity, was significant due to the

unanimous demand for greater cooperation and sympathy for Congress and an end to the policy of non-intervention. Gandhi Ji and front-rank congress leaders supported this, demonstrating full support for the conference. The Congress, led by radical elements, changed its approach in 1928, recognizing the existence of states as an integral part of the Indian nation. At its Calcutta session, the Congress deleted the clause relating to non-interference and urged the Princes to guarantee citizenship rights and responsible government to their people. The Congress assured the states' people of its sympathy and support in their struggle for legitimate objectives. This resolution was considered their Magna Carta by the state's people. The All India State People Conference, born synchronically with this event, became closer to the Congress and became a wing of the larger organization. In the mid-1930s, radical groups in Congress produced an unprecedented change in their approach. Congress leaders like Sardar Patel, Jawaharlal Nehru, Dr. Pattabhi Sitaramayya, Acharya Narendra Dev, Jay Prakash Narayan, and Yusuf Mehrali accentuated the cause of the state people. Nehru's ardent loyalty to the cause of the State people was apparent in his 1929 presidential address to the Lahore Congress, in which he asserted that the Indian states could not live apart from the rest of India. The Congress took a more favourable posture towards the states at its Jabalpur session in 1935, proclaiming that the interests of the Indian states were as vital to the Indian National Congress as those of British India and promising them their entire support in their quest for independence.

Impact of Indian National Congress and All India State Peoples Conference on Kashmir politics:

During the period of 1930–1946, the freedom struggle in Kashmir was significantly impacted by the Indian National Congress and the All India States People Conference. Resolutions adopted by the Congress at its Lahore session were also echoed in Kashmir. Hindus and Sikhs in J&K state, along with leaders from the Muslim Conference, Kashmiri Pandit Yuvak Sabha, and the Kashmir Congress Committee, agreed that the national movement in the state was inseparable from the national movement in India and came to the conclusion that all community unity was necessary in order to achieve a reasonable amount of political reform in the state. Also, a consensus was established that the freedom struggle inside the state needs to be oriented towards the national liberation movement in British India and the Indian states.

Before Congress abandoned its non-interference policy, Nehru was keen to extend full support to the freedom movement led by Sheikh Abdullah in Jammu and Kashmir. Kashmiri-born Pandit Prem Nath Bazaz had already established

contacts with top brass of the Congress leaders like Mahatma Gandhi and Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru, hoping to alter the Muslim majoritarian character of the Kashmiri movement. Bazaz acted as a mediator between the two parties, who had already won over Sheikh Mohammad Abdullah since the Cheshma Shahi Garden meeting in 1932. Many scholars on Kashmir credit Bazaz for his outstanding role in converting the movement into a secular one. After the Muslim Conference's third session in November 1934, Sheikh Abdullah went to Punjab and sought advice from Congress leader Dr. Saifuddin Kitchlew in Lahore. On his advice, he decided to take on nationalism and organize a broader movement in cooperation with non-Muslim communities in Jammu and Kashmir, aiming to gain support for the cause. The impact of this visit was to such an extent that in a press interview, Abdullah suggested for the people of Punjab "to avoid interference in the state's internal affairs and stated that his future plan is to work on the lines of Congress and intend to start an organization of the same kind on my return home." After returning from Punjab in 1935, Sheikh Abdullah contacted Prem Nath Bazaz, providing him with comprehensive information about discussions held with Saifuddin Kitchlew and future programs. H.L Saxena mentioned "from this time onwards, Bazaz became Sheikh Abdullah's sole friend, philosopher, and mentor in all his future ventures, as he had never had his own brains and had always been a tool in the hands of somebody or the other."

First and foremost, Abdullah and Bazaz thought that they needed their own newspaper in order to express and spread their own ideas. Accordingly, they founded the weekly newspaper *Hamdard* in Urdu on August 1, 1935, to spread their ideology of secularism, social democracy, and nationalism. The *Hamdard* gained popularity for its fight against orthodoxy, symbolizing democracy and unification of Kashmir's, regardless of caste or faith, advocating for responsible governance in the state. Dr. Saif-ud-Din Kitchloo inaugurated the first issue of *Hamdard* in Hazuribagh, aiming to integrate the Indian National Congress's policies and programs into Kashmir's politics. The paper served as the official mouthpiece for this policy, popularizing the Congress's nationalist and secular ideas, particularly of its most popular leader, Jawaharlal Nehru. With Bazaz at the driving seat, the Muslim Conference official publication, particularly *Hamdard*, denounced Punjabi Muslim "communal" organisations for misleading the Kashmiri movement and cautioned people to keep out of Punjabi politics. As a result, Sheikh Abdullah shifted towards pro-Congress politics and separated from Punjabi Muslim organisations in the mid-1930s, likely due to the Congress's socialist tendencies and interest in princely states that it had

acquired under its new leadership under Jawaharlal Nehru.

In 1935, India's political climate changed significantly, with the Government of India Act, 1935 proposing a federal scheme at the center. However, this plan failed to satisfy both Indian leadership and Princes. The All India States People Conference strongly opposed the resolution, condemning the proposed federation plan, which denied state people representation and lacked consultation at any stage. Both the INC and the AISPC opposed the move, calling it undemocratic, and demanded that all representatives for the Federal Legislature be chosen on the basis of a popular elective principle. The Lucknow Congress (1935) deemed the Act as an instrument "to the accompaniment of widespread repression and the suppression of civil liberties and designed to facilitate and perpetuate the domination and the exploitation of the people of India". The AISPC, in its Karachi session in 1936, condemned the proposed federal structure, which denied states' people the right to elect their representatives. The Muslim Conference, while not a party to this resolution, shared the AISPC's view that Maharajas should not join the federation without prior consultation with the people's representatives, and if states were required to do so, only elected representatives should have the right to sit in the federal legislature.

The leadership of the Kashmir freedom movement was significantly influenced by the development of the INC and AISPC. On December 28, 1935, a public meeting in Srinagar, presided over by Pandit P.N. Bazaz, honoured the INC for its fifty-year service to the nation. This event laid the groundwork for Congress to launch policies and programs vis-à-vis the ongoing freedom struggle in the state of Jammu and Kashmir. The All India States Peoples Conference in Karachi in 1936, led by Dr. Pattabhi Sitaramayya, marked a significant milestone in the struggle for freedom among the state's people. Pattabhi Sitaramayya in his presidential address said that: "the states Peoples' Conference . . . be organically related to the Congress and restate its creed linking the responsible government of the states' people as an integral factor of the Poorna Swaraj or complete independence of the Congress." Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru and former Congress president Rajendra Prasad also attended the conference, where Nehru emphasized India's unity and indivisibility, asserting that "the fight of the Congress for Indian independence also included the freedom of the people of the states also. If Congress attained Swaraj, the states people would inevitably share their liberation." This session was significant because it strengthened the relationship between Congress and the people of the states. The session

backed the state's people in their struggle for civil liberties. This event opened a new chapter in the state's people politics, creating organisational units to help them achieve goals. The 1938 Navasari Convention provided more evidence of this affinity and highlighted the intimate bond between Congress and the All India State Peoples Conference.

As already mentioned Bazaz, a fervent nationalist, aimed to put the Kashmir freedom movement under the control of the Indian National Congress. He corresponded with Mahatma Gandhi in May 1934, providing a comprehensive account of Kashmir's events and seeking his assistance. Mr. Gandhi replied to Bazaz on May 15, 1934, saying: "We are sowing as we have reaped, seeing that Kashmir is predominantly Muslim State it is bound one day to become a Musalman state." For the whole non-Muslim inhabitants of the state, Gandhi's response was nothing less than a terrible bombshell. Bazaz therefore approached Pandit Nehru, because he was very interested in the most recent events in Kashmir and regarded Kashmir to be his ancestral homeland. On July 7, 1936, Bazaz received an encouraging letter from Nehru in which he claimed that Kashmir formed an "integral part" of a larger national issue:

"It is clear that ultimate fate of Kashmir, as of the other Indian States, is bound up with that of India as a whole, so that the larger struggle for Indian independence governs the situation and the more or less local struggle in Kashmir must be viewed in the light of the Indian struggle..."

H. L. Sexena stated: "This extensive correspondence has had a long-lasting impact on Kashmir politics." An emboldened Bazaz intended to play his cards after successfully persuading an ever-willing Nehru to engage in Kashmir politics and encouraged at the rise of secular political consciousness among Kashmiri Muslims. He convinced Abdullah, who had severed ties with Indian Muslim organisations and was facing harsh criticism in Kashmir for this move, to extend a joint invitation to Nehru to visit Kashmir in 1936 in order to strengthen their efforts to establish a joint Hindu-Muslim national front in politics. However, Nehru was unable to visit the state personally, but a group of Congress leaders visited the state in 1936 to create a liaison with the leaders of different communities. Mr. Purushottam Das Tandon received a strong direction from Nehru in August 1936 to meet with S.M. Abdullah and P. N. Bazaz, ushering in a new chapter in the connections between the two active movements. In 1937, he was followed by two notable Congress leaders, Khan Abdul Gaffar Khan and K.M Ashraf, who aimed to bring the Kashmir Movement closer to the Indian National Congress. Many meetings with Kashmiri leaders were held for this reason. K.M Ashraf gave multiple speeches in support of nationalism and

collaborative Hindu-Muslim movements. The Kashmir Struggle for Freedom was boosted by progressive Indian leaders who considerably influenced S.M. Abdullah's political outlook. They also held extensive discussions with student unions, workers, and labourers, which led to the emergence of the Youth League, Mazdoor Sabha, and Kisan Sabha. Nehru also supported the labour movement. He wrote a letter to G.M. Sadiq in 1937 regarding the Silk Factory Workers agitation in which "he sends his good wishes to Mazdoor Sabha in its difficult task and encouraged them that Workers must remember that their strength lies in their organisation and they should try to strength their union." The close liaison between Muslim Conference leaders and Congress broadly influenced the people of J&K, aligning their movement with Indian nationalism. As a result of this persuasion, Sheikh Abdullah received an invitation extended by Pandit Nehru, president of the INC, and accordingly Abdullah departed for Peshawar in 1938. Sheikh Sahib and Pandit Nehru met for the first time at Lahore railway station, and their meetings focused on changing the character of the Kashmir freedom movement. Nehru indubitably recommended opening the doors of the Muslim Conference to non-Muslims and starting a new era in Kashmir politics. The leaders agreed that the movement would be patterned after the Indian National Congress. This face-to-face conversation had tremendous impact on the Sheikh Abdullah. It enhanced his conviction in a broad-minded approach towards the problem in Kashmir both political and economic. The meeting broadly advanced secular politics in Kashmir and dispelled Abdullah's doubts about the Indian National Congress's stance on the Kashmir freedom Movement. After returning from Peshawar, Abdullah explained to his party to reorganize the movement on national lines and change the nomenclature of the Muslim Conference to a national organization. But this move was opposed by anti-secular forces both inside and outside the state who criticized it as "a political bargaining" and the "double-edged" politics of the INC who wanted to please the Hindus. While some saw it as a significant step towards nationalist politics. Despite criticism, S.M Abdullah and other left-leaning forces continued with their program.

During the 1938 Navasari convention, state workers like P. N. Bazaz criticised the Congress Working Committee Resolution, which banned state congress committee formation in the States. Thanks to Dr. Pattabhi Sitarammaya's persistent efforts to bring the leadership of the Congress closer to the state people's movement, the resolution was suitably modified, and the convention prepared a draft resolution to meet the state people's viewpoint. It ran as follows:

"The Congress stands for the same political, social and economic freedom in the States as the rest of India and considers the states as an integral part of India, which can't be separated 'Purna Swaraj' or complete independence which is the objective of the Congress, is for the whole of India inclusive of the States, for the integrity and unity of India must be maintained in freedom as it has been maintained in subjection. The only kind of federation that can be accepted to the congress, is one in which the States participate as free units enjoying the measure of democratic freedom as the rest of India"

The draft was approved by Congress and officially moved as a resolution at the Haripura session in February 1938. The session ensured full responsible government and protection of civil liberties in states, condemning the absence of complete freedom and suppression of civil liberties in some states. The Congress expressed its sympathy for the people's quest for freedom and voiced hope that the day of their deliverance is not far away. The decision not only encouraged state people to organize themselves and continue their fight for freedom, but it also instilled complete trust in the people of the states in Congress. The policy of the Congress was now crystal-clear, aiming at active engagement in the people's fight for freedom in the states. This approach had an immediate and profound impact on the Jammu & Kashmir freedom struggle, changing the movement's community identity to one of a national character.

In February 1939, the All India States Peoples Conference, led by Nehru, held its session in Ludhiana. This event was pivotal in the State's People movement, as it sparked a nationwide awakening and made princely states aware of their rights. The conference spread the message of freedom and demanded responsible government and civil liberties in Indian states like Hyderabad, Kashmir, Travancore, and Mysore. In his presidential address, referring to the struggle of state peoples in the context of a larger nationalist movement in India, Nehru said, "The freedom of the people of the states is a big enough thing, yet it is a part of the larger freedom of India, and till we gain that larger freedom, it is a struggle for us." He further went on saying that the national awakening in the States has been a source of strength for the people of India in their struggle for freedom. He urged them to organize against communalism and oppression. Some dozens of leaders from Jammu & Kashmir state participated in this session. The Muslim Conference and Nationalist forces in J&K state praised President Nehru for his views on the freedom movement in Kashmir and Hyderabad. Nehru in a clear-cut said that the rulers in these states were acting as agents of British Imperialism,

using communal differences to suppress popular movements. Comparing the popular movements in both of the states, Nehru observed:

“...Hyderabad and Kashmir are two premier States in India and we might have hoped that they would set an example to others by introducing free institutions and responsible government. Unfortunately both are backward politically and socially. Hyderabad is a predominantly Hindu State with a Muslim ruling class; Kashmir is predominantly a Muslim state with a Hindu ruling class. Both these represent the same type of problems and both have some background of extreme poverty, illiteracy and undeveloped sources.”

Nehru emphasized to the Hindus of Kashmir that minorities should not fight for petty claims like administrative jobs and instead give up communal claims and share in service. Several resolutions were passed, including the "National Demand" manifesto, which supported constitutional reforms and envisioned socio-political change and economic outlook for the people of Jammu and Kashmir. The Ludhiana session significantly impacted Kashmir politics by ending political isolation and bringing the movement closer to Indian nationalism.

Sheikh Mohammad Abdullah was released from Muzaffarabad jail on 28 February 1939, along with other leaders. He went on a month-long tour outside the state to strengthen his relationship with the Indian National Congress. In March 1939, he was asked to preside over the Annual Session of All India State's Peoples Conference at Tripura, accompanied by Bakshi Ghulam Mohammad, Kashap Bandhu, Pandit Prem Nath Bazaz, and Maulana Mohammad Sayed Masoodi. State leaders in Kashmir established contacts with the country's leading nationalist political organization. Here at the session, the Kashmir leaders got a chance to meet personally to discuss their problems and address their issues with prominent leaders like Jawahar Lal Nehru, Sardar Patel, Bholabhai Desai, Babu Rajindra Prashad, Maulana Abul Kalam Azad, Dr. Syed Mehmood, and Jai Prakash Narayan. Sheikh Abdullah warned princes of the states in his presidential speech about the implications of the battle between oppression and democracy. He directed all Rajas and Nawabs that “they should make use of public resources for the welfare of their subjects and they should not spend money from the state treasuries for their personal dignity and splendor which are filled with blood and sweat of their poor subjects.” He promised to reorient his movement on the “basic Principles of the India National Congress”. It was due to the guidance and impact of the Indian National Congress that the Jammu and Kashmir Muslim Conference sheds its communal complexion and altered its name into the

National Conference on 11th June, 1939; and it was afterward affiliated to the All India States People's Conference.

The transformation of the Muslim Conference into the National Conference marked a significant shift in Kashmir's freedom movement, introducing an era of anti-British politics in the valley. The Kashmir movement evolved from a mere opposition to the maharaja's government to an anti-imperialist movement advocating for Indian subcontinent independence. It shifted towards the Indian National Congress, disappointing the Muslim League leadership and supporters. This new orientation led to contesting voices and narratives within the National Conference and Kashmir politics, with the organization's goal of achieving a responsible government in the state.

Nehru and other stalwart leaders visit to Kashmir:

In 1940, after the Muslim League adopted an alarming Pakistan Resolution, Sheikh Abdullah had to decide whether to affiliate himself with the Congress or the Muslim League, particularly while these two major Indian political parties were competing for winning over the National Conference. Events heavily favoured the Congress, which was ideologically opposed to the Muslim League. Consequently, Abdullah invited Pandit Nehru to visit Kashmir. Accordingly Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru accompanied by Khan Abdul Gaffar Khan, Mr. Padiya and Muhammad Younis reached in Srinagar on May 30, 1940. A meeting was held at Hazuri Bagh, Srinagar, to welcome Congress leaders, and Sheikh Abdullah referred to Pandit Nehru as "an illustrious son of the Valley of Kashmir." Abdullah highlighted the National Conference's commitment to fighting colonial dominance and exploitation while also emphasizing its loyalty to India's unity and freedom. Congress leaders praised the National Conference's efforts in forging a national struggle for freedom in the J&K State. Khan Abdul Gaffar and Pandit Nehru declared that "the people in India regardless of religion or location, were one nation, India was one and indivisible." Congress leaders announced that India's liberation from British rule would not involve replacing British rulers and officers with Indian ones, but rather transferring political power to the people of India. They assured the National Conference that the Indian people supported and stood with the people of the state in their quest for freedom. Nehru expressed his unequivocal support for the National Conference as the sole national organization in the state, similar to Jinnah's view of the Muslim Conference as the only representative body of state Muslims.

Pandit Nehru's ten-day visit to the Valley marked a significant turning point in S.M. Abdullah's political career and the history of

freedom struggle. The proximity of the National Conference to the Congress sharpened the political cleavage in Kashmir. The National Conference and Sheikh Abdullah for the first time came into the limelight, gaining attention both within the subcontinent and beyond its borders. S.M. Abdullah was propelled by these events to consider the potential assistance Congressmen could provide him if he could garner their support. He has decided to go the whole hog with Congress.

The Sopore Session of the National Conference of 1945:

Because of Jinnah's growing political influence and demand for Pakistan, he visited Kashmir valley in June 1944. The League President's judgment against the National Conference sparked widespread discontent among party members and they denounced Jinnah for his interference in Jammu and Kashmir politics. On 20 June, Sheikh Abdullah warned Jinnah in a demagogic utterance at Khanyar to leave Kashmir. "If Jinnah does not give up the habit of interfering in our politics it will be difficult for him to go back in an honourable manner" He also stated unequivocally that Jinnah's mission in Kashmir was an unmitigated failure. Sheikh Abdullah's popularity among Muslims has since declined; he invited top leaders of the National Congress and State Peoples Conference to participate in the annual session of the National Conference at Sopore on August 3, 4, and 5, 1945. Jawaharlal Nehru, Abul Kalam Azad, Khan Abdul Gaffar Khan, Mian Iftiqar-ud-Din, Asaf Ali, Kanya Lal Vaidya, Achal Ishwar Prasad and General Secretary Peoples Conference Jai Narayan Vayas arrived in Srinagar in July 1945. Abdullah's close association with Congress during the AISPC meetings led to his decision. In the session, the Congress leaders spoke at length and emphasised that the ideology of the Nationalists was the right one and that this party alone was the real representative of the people of the country. Khan Abdul Gaffar Khan inaugurated a session recognizing Sheikh Abdullah as the harbinger of Kashmir awakening and said that "Sheikh Mohammad Abdullah is the gift of God to the people of Kashmir, and if you don't follow him, they would suffer terrible hardships." Nehru promised the Indian National Congress's support for the battle against autocratic rule in the state and appealed non-Muslims to join the National Conference in large numbers to achieve the goal. Maulana Azad assured Congress's full support for Sheikh Abdullah in his national activities. Sheikh Abdullah's presidential address highlighted the National Conference's struggle for political emancipation in Jammu and Kashmir, stating it was the only path to liberating forty lakh people of the state. He emphasized that "the future and independence of Jammu and Kashmir State were inextricably linked with the

future and independence of India." In his presidential address, he outlines the programme for building up "New Kashmir."

The Sopore annual session of the National Conference was significant in the annals of the freedom struggle of Jammu and Kashmir due to its attendance by prominent Indian Nationalists. The National Conference was the first Indian subcontinent Nationalist organization to pass a resolution supporting self-determination. It is worth noting that the All India Congress Committee passed the resolution of self-determination following the Sopore session of the National Conference (1945).

The Standing Committee of the All India States People's Conference met in Kashmir on August 6, 1945, praising the National Conference's success in awakening and organizing the state's masses. The committee appreciated the broad vision of the Jammu and Kashmir National Conference, its leaders, and President Sheikh Mohammad Abdullah, who aimed to build a national organization to transform the state into a prosperous and new Kashmir based on the progress and well-being of the masses. The Standing Committee affirmed that states are an integral part of India and that major states can form "democratic and autonomous units in a free and federated India". They adopted a resolution on the rights of the state's people which reads as:

"The Standing Committee reiterates that the goal of the people of the states is the establishment of fully responsible government in the states as integral parts of India, with major states forming democratic autonomous units in a free and federated India..."

The national conference supported the AISPC throughout its existence, and Sheikh Abdullah was chosen as its vice president in 1946. Regardless of how the region's subsequent history unfolded, there is no doubt that this was not only a reflection of Abdullah's status among the State's people's leadership but also of Jammu and Kashmir's vital position within India's broader national movement, which now encompassed the domains of the native rulers and princes.

Conclusion:

The Indian National Congress's involvement in Kashmir politics in the mid-1930s, along with its close affinity with the All India States Peoples Conference, considerably impacted the Kashmir freedom struggle. The proximity of the National Conference to the Congress sharpened the political cleavage in Kashmir, shifting the movement from a communal to a national character. Furthermore, the Nehru-Abdullah alliance was a significant event that took away all remaining ambiguity in Abdullah's mind with regard to the Congress's future approach towards the freedom

struggle, thereby signaling the advent of Kashmir's secular political movement. The conversion of the Muslim Conference into the National Conference was an important contribution of the Kashmir freedom struggle to Indian secular politics. The party initiated an anti-despotic, anti-colonial, and progressive movement, taking a fundamental national direction. The Kashmir freedom movement, as an integral part of the Indian liberation movement, fought for national emancipation from British colonial rule and the destruction of their colonial framework in the Indian States.

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